

A Task Priority Framework for Cooperative Manipulation and Transportation

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Abstract—This paper presents the work done at University of Genova on mobile manipulation. The task priority architecture, employed for the control of a single agent, is first recalled as a basis for solving a cooperative transportation task.

Index Terms—cooperative mobile manipulation, task priority framework, mobile manipulators.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the late 80s, an important research trend has been the control of redundant systems and, in particular, how to effectively exploit their redundancy. The task-based control [1] was proposed as a mean to specify control objectives in a coordinate system that is directly relevant to the task that needs to be performed, rather than in the generalized coordinates of the robotic system, and was immediately enhanced by the introduction of the concept of task priority [2]. However, in those works the position control of the end-effector was always the highest priority task, and safety tasks such as joint limits were only *attempted* at lower priority. The reason was that such a framework did not encompass the possibility of handling inequality control objectives without overconstraining the system, and thus they could only be seen as “optimizations” to be done after the end-effector position task was executed. Only around 10 years ago, new control frameworks began to be developed to lift such a limitation [3], [4].

In this context, the GRAAL research group at University of Genova began tackling the problem of the coordinated control of a floating base and a manipulator for performing autonomous floating intervention [5] within the FP7 project TRIDENT. A novel task priority resolution mechanism, which managed equality and scalar-only inequality control objectives, was developed and experimentally tested in a blackbox recovery intervention in a harbour environment. Successively, the concepts developed in the TRIDENT project were further enhanced within the MARIS project, with the definition of a task priority framework able to activate and deactivate equality/inequality control objectives of any dimension (i.e. not limited to scalar ones) depending on the system current needs [6]. This feature allows the user to put safety and operational-enabling objectives at the highest priority, as they should be. Experiments in free floating grasping have been conducted, with multiple attempts to test the repeatability and robustness of the control [7].

Fig. 1. The overall architecture.

The aforementioned results were achieved with an overall control architecture split into two hierarchical levels, namely: a Kinematic Control Layer (KCL), in charge of generating the reference system velocities, taking into account all the control objectives of the system, including the desired motion of the object and internal wrenches; and a Dynamic Control Layer (DCL), in charge of tracking the reference system velocity vector, generating the actuation commands, as in Fig. 1. Hence, the results were not limited to underwater vehicle manipulator systems, but could be applied to any robotic structure, including dual arm systems and ground mobile manipulators [8].

The single agent Task Priority Inverse Kinematics (TPIK) procedure developed during these years is thus characterized by the following features: 1) possibility of activating and deactivating control tasks, treating inequality objectives efficiently, 2) a proper arm-vehicle coordination scheme, preventing unavoidable minor accuracies and disturbances affecting the mobile platform, such as delayed or imprecise wheel actuation, to propagate through the coupled kinematics immediately to the end effectors, 3) possibility of multi-rate control, 4) ability to deal with under-actuated systems uniformly, 5) deterministic computational time. These results are summarized in [9].

II. COOPERATIVE MANIPULATION

In the last few years, cooperative manipulation and transportation has become one of the most important research topics on multi-robot systems [10]. Given the advantages that task priority based approaches bring to the control of a single-agent, it becomes interesting and important from a practical point of view to devise cooperative solutions

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the cooperative manipulation algorithm.

that could fully exploit the task-priority based KCLs already embedded within each agent. The idea developed in this work is to suitably coordinating them through a minimal data exchange, allowing an efficient execution of the cooperative manipulation/transportation task, while maintaining the safety needs of each individual agent and of the global constrained system at the highest priority.

The proposed coordination algorithm is based on the following main steps, sketched in Fig. 2. First, each agent, separately solves a TPIK problem as if it were the sole one acting on the object, with its original task hierarchy having safety and prerequisite tasks located at higher priority than the tool control point motion. At the end of this procedure, the optimal system velocity vector $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i$ is used to compute the Cartesian velocity that the agent would impose to the object if it were alone, i.e., the *non-cooperative* tool-frame velocities $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t,i} = \mathbf{J}_{t,i}\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i$, $i = a, b..$ These velocities are exchanged between the agents, and each agent evaluates, in a *distributed* way, the *cooperative* tool-frame velocity vector

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_t &= \frac{1}{\mu_a + \mu_b} (\mu_a \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t,a} + \mu_b \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t,b}), \\ \mu_a &= \mu_0 + \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t,a}\| \triangleq \mu_0 + \|e_a\|, \\ \mu_b &= \mu_0 + \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t,b}\| \triangleq \mu_0 + \|e_b\|, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with $\mu_0 > 0$ and where the norms $\|e_i\|$ serve as a measure of the difficulties that agent i has in tracking the original object reference velocity, due to higher priority safety and prerequisite tasks. Thus, with the above weighting choice, the resulting cooperative velocity $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t$ will be closer to the one evaluated by the agent exhibiting the greatest difficulty in tracking the original desired object velocity, than to the one evaluated by the other agent. For example, in case $\|e_a\|/\|e_b\| \rightarrow \infty$, then $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t \rightarrow \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t,a}$, which implies that agent a progressively imposes its non-cooperative tool-frame velocity as the cooperative one. Consequently, agent b will progressively follow what is imposed by agent a at the Cartesian level. Such a situation, and its opposite one, correspond to the extreme cases. In all the other situations, the weighting rule (1) provides an adequate compromise.

The cooperative *cooperative* tool-frame velocity is then projected in the end-effectors constrained motion subspace, obtaining the so-called *feasible cooperative* velocity vector. Details of such a projection are here omitted for sake of brevity. Finally, both agents separately run a new TPIK procedure with the original task-priority hierarchy now modified

Fig. 3. Obstacle avoidance experiment: snapshots of the two YouBots as they cooperatively avoid the obstacle and reach the desired final position.

into the one having the non-reactive tool-frame velocity tracking of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t$ at the *highest* priority. In this way, both systems independently optimize their safety tasks under the imposed constraint of the common tool frame velocity. Figure 3 show a few snapshots of an experiment with two YouBot mobile manipulators. The two agents need to transport the object to a goal position, however the agent on the left has an obstacle in its path. The two agents successfully coordinate themselves to avoid it since, thanks to the proposed coordination policy, the agent on the left automatically becomes the leader while the other follows it in the avoidance manoeuvre.

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